

Data-driven topology optimisation for energy-absorbing structures

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Motivation of using lightweight materials

F. Czerwinski, Materials, 2021.

What are Impact Energy absorbers?!

Queen Mary
University of London

WARNING:
Don't try this at home!

Cellular structures/materials

Ashby chart

Graded lattice structures

Graded lattice structures

Uniform lattice structures

Uniform lattice structures

Lattice liners for helmets

Graded lattice liner vs EPS liner

Lattice vs Spinodoids

Spinodoids topology = $f(\bar{\rho}, \theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3)$

$(\bar{\rho}, \theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3)$

MATLAB

Experimental tests

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Experimental results: Carbon_P

FE Modelling

- Hill plastic anisotropic model.
- Tetrahedral Elements
- General contact:
 - Contact between the specimen and the anvil and the loading upper plate
 - Self contact: internal surfaces contacting each other.
- Maximum strain failure.

FEM vs Experiments-PETG

Optimisation

Objectives: Crush efficiency & Energy absorption

$$e_E = \frac{E_{\text{absorb}}}{P_{\max} L_0} \approx \frac{P_m \delta_{\max}}{P_{\max} L_0}$$

Strong correlation between ρ and the objective functions despite the others!

$\rho = 40\%$

● Mix ● Lamellar ● Cubic ● Isotropic ● Columnar

Why Bayesian optimisation?!

Step: Step 1 Frames: 9
Total Time: 0.000000

Why Bayesian optimisation?!

- ❑ Highly nonlinear relationship between the topology and mechanical response.
- ❑ Computationally expensive.
- ❑ Large design space

Bayesian optimisation

$$\text{Bayes's Theorem } P(A|B) = \frac{P(A|B)P(A)}{P(B)}$$
$$P\left(E_A^{max} \mid \left[\rho, \theta_i^{i=1,2,3}\right]\right)$$

$\Sigma_{i,j}$: Covariance: how x_i and x_j are correlated

$$P(x; \mu, \Sigma) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{\frac{d}{2}} |\Sigma|} e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left((x - \mu)^T \Sigma^{-1} (x - \mu) \right)}$$

We use Kernel function to estimate $\Sigma_{i,j}$

Results of the Optimisation

Optimisation: 1 Objective function & 3 variables

Single VS Multi objective function

- Objective functions: Crush efficiency and Energy absorption.
- Converging much quicker in the case of multi-objective optimisation.

Single Objective

Multi Objective

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Experimental tests

- Material characterization
- Crushing spinodal structures

FE modelling

- The results of FEM are in good agreement with the experimental tests results.

Optimisation

- A data-driven optimisation framework has been developed for multi-objective topology optimisation of spinodal structures.
- The framework has been successfully used to find the best spinodal structure to maximise CE and EA simultaneously.

Future work

- Scale up the framework for larger structures featuring different types of spinodal structures at different points.

github.com/MCM-QMUL/CELLCOMP

Thanks!

**Engineering and
Physical Sciences
Research Council**

FEM vs Experiments-PETG: Columnar

